

Application of ethyl cinnamate based optical tissue clearing and expansion microscopy combined with retrograde perfusion for 3D lung imaging

Quanchao Sun^{a,b,c}, Picascia Tiziana^{a,c}, Arif ul Maula Khan^{a,c}, Cinzia Brenna^{a,c}, Vincent Heuveline^d, Anja Schmaus^{e,f}, Jonathan P. Sleeman^{e,f} and Norbert Gretz^{a,c*}

*Corresponding author: Norbert Gretz, e-mail: Norbert.Gretz@medma.uni-heidelberg.de;
Medical Research Center, Medical Faculty Mannheim, University of Heidelberg, Theodor-Kutzer-Ufer 1-3, 68167, Mannheim, Germany

1. Supplementary Movies:

Movie 1 (related to Figure 5). The movie demonstrates 3D high-resolution structure of alveoli (red: anti-CD31 antibody stained capillaries; green: anti-AQP5 antibody stained alveolar interstitium).

Movie 2 (related to Figure 6). The movie demonstrates 3D visualization of bronchial cilia stained with anti- α -Ac-Tub antibody (red) in a thick lung slice (green: autofluorescence).

Movie 3 (related to Figure 8). The movie demonstrates 3D imaging of paraffin-embedded lung metastases tissue co-stained with Sytox green and anti-CD31 antibody after ExM (blue: nuclear; red: anti-CD31 antibody stained capillaries).

The DOI of movies: [10.6084/m9.figshare.12453635](https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.12453635)

2. Supplementary Figures:

Supplementary Figure 1

Supplementary Figure 2

Supplementary Figure 3

Supplementary Figure 4

Supplementary Figure 5

Supplementary Figure 6

Supplementary Figure 7

Supplementary Figure 8

Supplementary Figure 1. 3D visualization of anti-CD31 antibody immunofluorescence labeled vasculature in normal lung processed by ECi based OTC (LCFM, 20× objective). The arrows indicate lung vasculature and the asterisks indicate deformed alveoli in the tissue. (A) Overlay image of the autofluorescence (green) and anti-CD31 antibody stained vasculature (red), which was labeled before ECi based OTC. (B) One focal plane of Figure A demonstrated the lung vasculature and deformed alveoli by immunofluorescence staining before ECi based OTC. (C) Overlay image of the autofluorescence (green) and anti-CD31 antibody stained vasculature (red), which was labeled after ECi based OTC. (D) One focal plane of Figure C demonstrated the lung vasculature and deformed alveoli by immunofluorescence staining after ECi based OTC.

Supplementary Figure 2. 2D focal planes of the Figure 2C and Figure 4B demonstrated that the size deformations after ECi based OTC (without immunofluorescence staining) and ExM protocol did not change the alveolar morphology. (A) One focal plane of Figure 2C demonstrated that the morphology of alveoli (white arrows) were well preserved after MHI148-PEI labeled vasculature (red) in normal lung processed by ECi based clearing. Green: autofluorescence. (B) One focal plane of Figure 4B showed that the morphology of alveoli (yellow arrows) stained with anti-AQP5 antibody (white) were not deformed after ExM.

Supplementary Figure 3. Depth coding image of the Figure 4D indicated the z-dimension.

Supplementary Figure 4. Depth coding image of the Figure 5 indicated the z-dimension.

Supplementary Figure 5. Depth coding image of the Figure 6 indicated the z-dimension.

Supplementary Figure 6. Depth coding image of the Figure 7A indicated the z-dimension.

Supplementary Figure 7. Depth coding image of the Figure 8B indicated the z-dimension.

Supplementary Figure 8. Depth coding image of the Figure 9 indicated the z-dimension.

3. The original images that had been showed in the form of collection in the manuscript and supplement.

Figure 1A

Figure 1B

Figure 2A

Figure 2B

Figure 2C

Figure 2D

Figure 3A

Figure 3B

Figure 3C

Figure 3D

Figure 4A

Figure 4B

Figure 4C

Figure 4D

Figure 7A

Figure 7B

Figure 7C

Figure 8A

Figure 8B

Figure 8C

Figure 10A

Figure 10B

Figure 10C

Distribution of cells using 40x40 boxes: SMOOTHED by GAUSSIAN with Std Deviation = 2 $\times 10^4$

Supplementary Figure 1A

Supplementary Figure 1B

Supplementary Figure 1C

Supplementary Figure 1D

Supplementary Figure 2A

Supplementary Figure 2B

